

Different Techniques of Improving Teaching Foreign Languages

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the methods of teaching foreign languages and the role of a teacher in teaching language learners in groups. It also gives some tips for the improvement of educational process.*

Key words: *quality of education, interactive methods, modern technology, motivation, educational resources, spreadsheets, information, training, authentic video, animation films, visual support, social process, language skills, target language, classroom management.*

Introduction

When planning our lessons, we decide which way of grouping learners of interaction patterns to use. The interaction patterns we choose depend on the learners and their learning styles, our own teaching style(s) and preferences, the teaching approach, the learning context, the type of activity, the aim or learning purpose of the activity and the stage in the lesson. There are many different interaction patterns to choose from, whole class (the teacher leads the class and the learners focus on the teachers), individuals open pairs (two learners do a pair work activity in front of class), groups, teams, mingles. Very often, the activity itself suggest a particular interaction pattern.

The success of modern technology reinforces teachers and students with good language materials and brings color to the language classroom, and the language becomes more authentic than in previous periods of its teaching. Sure, books are important language learning tools, but new technology has a bigger impact on learners.

Motivation is an important issue in language teaching. It encourages and generates enthusiasm in learning foreign languages. A long period of learning foreign languages and accumulated experience show that if there is no motivation or interest in the subject, no one and nothing can do anything and achieve anything in any field. According to Clifford, the teacher is not the only audience for student presentations. Students are often expected to present their work and receive feedback from their peers and those around them outside of their class. Whether they are using presentation software to accompany a face-to-face presentation or developing materials to post online, the trend is for students to communicate and defend their work in front of a wide audience. This enhances students' understanding that problem-based learning is real work for real audiences. The use of technology to find and present educational problems is an important issue. One of the main challenges for teachers interested in problem-based learning is identifying problems that are appropriate for their students and the topics they need to learn.

Methodology

The use of technology to summarize and present results is also important in motivation. In the past, students memorized and used formulas and models created by others to solve problems. Students often used these formulas, especially in the early stages of learning, with little understanding. At the beginning of the 21st century, computer tools provide students with the opportunity to create and test their own models using tools such as spreadsheets or concept maps. This type of learning deepens students' understanding of abstract concepts and allows these concepts to be learned at an earlier age. After students summarize their data and other information, they usually communicate their findings to others. In the past, this meant writing a report for the teacher to read.

Video is a powerful tool to help English learners improve their language skills. They provide the learner with content, context, and language. Video will play a big role for students in the classroom as well as in self-study situations. Children learn better if they are positive about what they are doing and if they are motivated or willing to do it. One way to provide or enhance this motivation is to use a video that is enjoyable and motivating to learn the language. Video presents language not only in context, but also in a way that can influence learners to "grab" their attention in a way that is not possible with static text or audio-only recording.

One of the goals of teaching English to young children is to instill in them the idea that language learning is a happy experience and that video creates an engaging, enjoyable learning environment. The younger language learners are still learning about the world around them. Young children love listening to stories over and over again, and the same goes for videos. By watching the video several times, children can learn absorption and imitation.

Results and discussion

Benefits of video/movies, television and other broadcast media:

1. This is a very useful resource as it is natural and authentic.
2. It also prepares students for authentic communication.
3. Students quickly become aware of the richness and complexity of the English language.
4. Students see that English is not only an object of academic interest, but the key to success in their professional lives.
5. English becomes a real means of communication and communication between students.
6. Students demonstrate progress in several skills at the same time.
7. The video can be used at any level of language proficiency for both beginners and advanced students.
8. With careful selection and purposeful planning, this can be very motivating for students.

Video conveys meaning better than other media. The video presents the language in context in a way that the cassette cannot. Students can see who (or what!) is speaking, where the speakers are, what they are doing, etc. All of these visual cues can aid understanding. Video represents a positive use of technology. Teenagers, in particular, have a positive attitude towards television and video. It is seen as "modern" compared to the books. Once the decision has been made to use video in the classroom, one should think about what purpose the video is being used for video role. The way video is used and the materials prepared for use with video will depend on the role the video is to play.

However, a video sequence workflow may include more than one of these roles. Students can watch the video to find out information about, for example, a famous person. The same lesson may also include listening activities so that students can extract relevant information. This can be used to develop vocabulary about "life".

When choosing videos, consider the following factors:

Sound and picture quality:

Audio quality is especially important as language learners benefit little from a video they cannot hear. Another important factor is the availability related print materials that can be used to develop activities that support and expand the language used in the video.

Video support extension:

When considering visual support, care should be taken to select material in which the soundtrack and pictures "converge". McWilliam, for example, cites research showing that if there is a mismatch between visual and auditory messages, then viewers (especially children) will ignore the language context.

Completeness:

Tomalin "The perfect video clip... tells the full story or section of the story." This idea of fullness is important for young learners whose primary motivation for watching videos is enjoyment.

Length:

The length of the clip is important, it should not be too long, perhaps from 30 seconds to 10 minutes, depending on the purpose of the training.

Content compliance:

The content should be suitable for young learners. How the video was rated; "Universal", "Parental guidance", for age "13" or "18"? Is the video suitable for viewing in all cultures?

Language content:

When using video to represent language, an important factor to consider is the language elements (specific grammatical structures, language features, or colloquial expressions) presented on stage.

According to many teachers, students seem to become more interested in language learning when it comes to videos, especially genuine videos. Feature films capture students' attention with dazzling Hollywood effects, and since they are not intended for educational purposes, they reflect the authentic use of the target language. However, due to the authenticity of the language, teachers tend to restrict the use of feature films in intermediate and advanced classrooms. Some instructors prefer to work with video clips rather than the whole movie.

An authentic feature film brings enhanced context and interesting content to the classroom. When using a film, the oral skills course and other skills courses may be combined through the use of common themes, features, and/or grammar presented in the film. Although listening classes in oral skills textbooks may have a common theme, they are unlikely to contain much intriguing content at an elementary level. Also, text actions, unlike movies, are often disabled.

The use of film, however, provides a rich context through which students can improve understanding and practice listening and speaking, noting that the extended context, interesting content, rich visual imagery, and often exaggerated film actions and gestures provide students with a multi-sensory experience. an entrance that is close to what they would find in real life communication. Such visual input engages and motivates students, and through the film's many contextual cues, helps students understand the language used in the film.

Tips for language teaching:

- Assessment can affect what we teach, how we teach and our learners' motivation for learning. It is very important for tests to have a good influence on teaching and learning.
- Some assessment tasks are easy to write, e.g. essay titles, or mark, e.g. categorizing tasks. But we need to check if they reflect what we have taught. It is not a good idea to use a particular testing task just because it is easy to use or easy to mark. For example, for administrative reasons, it is often difficult to assess learners' speaking, so speaking is often not assessed, and as

a result learners may start thinking that speaking isn't important. Speaking skills can sometimes be more easily assessed informally than formally.

- To really reflect the level of learners' learning, the content and tasks included in progress and summative tests should reflect the content and tasks in our teaching, this may mean that our tests include a mixture of objective and subjective tasks.
- Assessment needs to be fair. This means that progress and summative test should only test what has been taught and that they should be reliable and accurate in their marking. Using bands to help us mark subjective tasks helps achieve this.
- Feedback to learners on what they got right or wrong, their strengths and weaknesses, and what they can do to improve, is very important. Through feedback, assessment helps learning.

Conclusion

Informal assessment is often much more suitable for assessing young learners than formal assessment. This is because young learners' ways of thinking and learning are based on experiencing and communicating, and also because teachers of young learners are often interested in finding out more about their learners' attitudes, motivation and behaviors.

If in your school, several classes follow the same syllabus or coursebook and do the same subjective / partly subjective test it is useful for the teachers to use the same assessment criteria or bands. It may be useful to agree what mark you would give to some samples of students' writing before marking starts. Even then, there may be disagreements amongst teachers. At this point, it's useful to discuss exactly what the bands mean. This process helps marking become fairer and more reliable.

Working with assessment criteria and bands helps the teacher grade all students against the same level of achievement. This can help the teacher and the students know more about their real level of ability than if the teacher just ranks the students according to their grades.

In short, the use of the latest technologies and the use of interactive methods are important in improving the quality of education and providing high quality education to students.

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